

Study of binary liquid capillary bridges stretched between two solid flat surfaces

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Abstract: Liquid capillary bridges (CBs), created between two flat solid surfaces, parallel to each other, are of significant importance for number of scientific and industrial applications. In this paper, we present our experimental investigation of the liquid CBs at stretching, created by two immiscible liquids: cedar oil–water and paraffin–water with common interface. The behaviour of these binary structures was studied and compared with that of the single liquid CBs. It was found that the binary liquid CBs exist in the same definition domain as the single liquid CBs. Moreover, the current paper is focused not only on static, but also on non-equilibrium behaviour of CBs. We demonstrate that the binary liquid CBs can be engineered by the proper combination of polar (water) and non-polar (oil) fluids and these CBs exist within the theoretically predicted domain. The experimental results of water/cedar oil and water/paraffin binary CBs shows that the paraffin spreads in water surface and modifies the overall surface tension of the system, while the cedar oil and water retain their surface properties within the binary structure.

Keywords: BINARY, LIQUID, DEFINITION DOMAIN, STRETCHING, CAPILLARY BRIDGES

1. Introduction

Behavior of liquid capillary bridges (CBs), created between two solid surfaces is a topic that attracts the attention of mathematicians and physicists more than two hundred years. These shapes possess constant mean surface curvature, a property discovered by the French astronomer C. Delanay [1]. The ability of liquid water to create CBs was known and used by the ancient civilizations (as example on the walls in the tomb of the Egyptian nomarch, Djehutihotep is depicted a scene of a deliberately CBs creation in order to be increased the stiffness of the sand during the transportation of a colossal statue [2]).

Investigation of CBs at stretching is a well-known approach in their analysis. This approach reveals not only their ability to exist but also the possible ways for industrial applications such as soldering [3], tire adhesion to road [4] etc. as well as self-assemblies of particles in liquid films [5].

CBs breakage can be investigated in two directions: The first one is dedicated to investigation of CBs instabilities, originally proposed by Rayleigh, [6]. Over the years various authors contributed to this topic [7-15]. The second direction is based on their pure static behavior. Stretching the bridge with constant volume as a set of steady-state states, at different height, where the height is increased until the breakage took place. In our previous papers [16-18], we theoretically show that the liquid bridge between two flat solid surfaces can exist within mathematically defined boundary, that we call a *definition domain*. Additionally, we introduce the curves formed with equal contact angles, isogones (see below Fig. 3&4).

Current paper extends these studies to non-equilibrium behavior of the CBs during their stretching. Chapter two summarizes the theoretical background for the current analysis. Chapters three and four present our experimental procedure as well as the used materials and the design of the equipment. Chapter four describes our experimental approach. The obtained results are presented in "Results and discussion" chapter. Finally, Chapter six summarizes the results and conclusions, based on them.

2. Theoretical background

The subject of our investigation is CBs in conditions of lack of gravity, sketched in Fig. 1. The geometry equation that needs to be solved, was formulated by Princen, [19] and in dimensionless form [17] is:

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \mp \frac{C(x^2 - 1) + 1}{\sqrt{x^2 - [C(x^2 - 1) + 1]^2}} \quad 1$$

where $x = \frac{r}{r_m}$ and $y = \frac{z}{r_m}$ are dimensionless cylindrical coordinates, r is the current radius, z is the axial coordinate, both

scaled by r_m (the CB waist radius). The parameter C is the dimensionless capillary pressure: $C = \frac{X \sin \theta - 1}{X^2 - 1} \equiv \Delta P \frac{r_m}{2\sigma}$, where σ is the surface tension [17].

Previously, we developed a theoretical approach for analysis of stretching behavior of a capillary bridge between two flat surfaces. We derived two important equations, related to the dimensionless dependence of height and volume from the radius. We introduced the dimensionless contact line radius $X = \frac{R}{r_m}$, and R , dimensional contact line radius [17]. In the current paper we analyze experimentally obtained data in relation of the dimensionless height to dimensionless coordinate X , which is in the theoretical form as follows:

$$\frac{h}{r_m} = \frac{\pi}{4C} - \frac{1}{2C} \operatorname{asin} \left[\frac{\frac{(1-2C)}{2C^2} - (X^2 - 1)}{\frac{(1-2C)}{2C^2}} \right] - I_0(X, C) \quad 2$$

The dimensionless parameter $I_0(X, C)$ cannot be integrated analytically:

$$I_0(X, C) = \int_1^X \frac{1 + [\xi^2(C - 1)]}{\sqrt{\xi^2 - [\xi^2(C - 1)]^2}} d\xi \quad 2$$

However, suitable numerical methods for integration can be applied if needed and based on this we calculated the isogones (black and grey curves in Figs. 3&4). These curves are very helpful in order to investigate the theoretical contact angle relation to the experimental data. They outline the CBs characteristics at static and quasi-static stretching conditions. In our previous papers [17, 18], we performed the experimental verification of this approach which is a reliable alternative to the traditional solution as mentioned in [5, 19], where incomplete elliptic integrals [20-22] are involved.

3. Materials experimental setup and method

Materials

In the current study, we used distilled water, cedar oil (CAS-No. 8000-27-9, R:38 by VALERUS) for microscopic applications and liquid paraffin (CHEMAX PHARMA) for pharmaceutical application, made according to Ph. Eur [0240]. The physical properties of the liquids are summarized in Tab. 1. The oils possess density slightly lower than the water density. The viscosity of cedar oil is more than 10 times higher than the liquid paraffin at 20 °C. Because the refractive indexes of both oils are higher than the refractive index of water, then they could be distinguished on the optical images.

Table 1: Physical properties of the liquids used in the experiments [23, 24, 25].

	Cedar oil (CO)	Paraffin (PO)	Water
Contents	Thujopsene (27.6%), Cedrol (15.8%), α - Cedrene (27.2%), β - Cedrene (7.3%), α - Copaene (6.3%) Widrol (1%)	methane series mixture, C_nH_{2n+2}	
refractive index $n_{20/D}$	1.519	1.473	1.333
Viscosity, mPa.s (20°C)	2000-5000	100-145	1.0
HLB	16.7	10.5	
Surface tension mN/m:			
• to water	0.5	50.5	
• to air	31.4	45.1	72.7
Density, g/cm ³	0.940-1.000	0,827 - 0,89	1.0

Experimental setup

The following equipment was acquired and assembled for the purpose of the investigation: The specially designed cell, consists of two supporting plates: The lower, Fig. 1(1), is fixed and the upper one, Fig. 1(2) can be moved in controllable way on z-axis (up and down) by a micrometric screw (5). On the plates are placed special type supporting tables, Fig. 1, upper (3) and lower (4), which in the current investigation hold pre-cleaned glasses 22x22 mm of thickness: 0.13 – 0.16 mm (cover glass for microscopy by Deltalab). The glass plates are replaced before each new droplet deposition for a CB creation. The recording camera is HAYEAR 16MP 1080P 60FPS USB C-mount, 3M sensor, 1080P output, with 60 fps recording speed. The optical system allows to be recorded images in polarized light, which significantly increases the contrast of recorded images. The entire equipment is installed on four-axis precise positioning system, which allows us to achieve very high precision in positioning of the camera toward the analyzed structures.

Method and the procedure

The concept of binary liquids usage in CBs study is not new, see Ref. [26]. Unlike the other methods, we control the volumes of each liquid, as well as their common contact interface by stretching. The method of study in this investigation is optical recording of the created CBs during their stretching until a breakage takes place. The obtained images are recorded with a speed of 60 fps. The selected frames from the records are analyzed by the help of the software IMAGEJ, [27].

Fig. 1. Sketch of the experimental setup: (1) lower support plate, (2) upper support plate, (3) and (4), plates (substrates) where are placed the glass substrates (5) micrometric manual control.

The procedure of a single CB creation is well described in our previous papers [17-18]. The actual procedure for creation of a binary CBs involves placement of a pendant droplet on the upper plate (4) and another, sessile on the lower plate (3), exactly below the sessile one. One of them is made by the selected oils and the other by water. In case of single liquid capillary bridge creation, only one droplet is placed on the bottom plate (3), Fig. 1. Using the micrometric control, the two droplets approach each other, until a common oil/water interface is created. In this way, the binary CB is formed, and its further stretching is subject of our investigation. The newly created bridge is compressed until the generatrix takes the

shape of a part of a circle [17]. After several minutes waiting for equilibration, manually, with constant speed, an increase of the CBs height take place until a breakage occurs. This, entire process is recorded by the camera and the obtained video is used for further analysis.

4. Experimental approach

In our previous papers, we demonstrated that independently from the type of the bridge (single or binary), if expanded quasistatic way (as a number of static states) during its height increase, the break-up is initiated around the boundary of the definition domain (Fig. 3&4). We found previously that in the static cases the three phase contact angles at the supporting plates do not depend significantly on the used liquids. In the stretching at that case, they do not change [16]

Current experimental study involves stretching of two types of CBs: First, we create a single-liquid capillary bridge (Fig. 2a) in order to identify the breakup boundaries, applied on pure liquids. We continuously increase the height without stopping for equilibration (unlike the approach for stretching applied in previous papers [17-18]). We investigate three different liquids: distilled water, cedar oil and liquid paraffine (oil). The increase of the CBs height was performed in three different constant speeds for sensitivity study of the breakage, as a function of the speed. As a result, boundary cases of pure liquid are outlined.

Fig. 2 Schematics of CBs, stretched between two solid flat surfaces: a) created from a single liquid drop; b) created from two liquid drops, one of them water and the other is from oil.

At the second step, we create binary liquid bridges in combination of polar and nonpolar liquids, as shown in Fig. 2b. The possibility, to create such a bridge, that the volumes of two droplets are equal is very low (the contact surface A_0 , Fig. 2b), therefore we consider sensitivity studies, of two combinations (Fig. 2b): upper volume smaller than lower volume (B_0 contact surface) and opposite, where the liquids interface is expected to be the contact surface B_1 . Further, two separate cases of upper droplet made from non-nonpolar liquid while the lower volume is made from the polar liquid and the opposite, see Tab. 2. This way, we investigated the change of stretching properties of the modified CBs.

We are looking to investigate the behavior of surface modified liquid. Comparison of the of binary liquid bridge to corresponding single liquid bridge stretching properties is an essential part of the study. Finally, we look for reproducibility of the stretching measurements, to obtain reliable results.

5. Results and discussion

The selection of initial sizes of droplets is presented in Tab. 2. There are considered eight binary cases: four of them are created with bigger size of the water droplet and the remaining are created with bigger size of the oil droplet. The column "Behavior" indicates the water and oil volume difference (Tab. 2). The sign "-" indicates the bigger oil volume than the volume of the water. In order to study the sensitivity of this approach, in four of the cases the pendant droplet is made by water, while in remaining cases, the oil

droplets are placed pendant. The opposing sessile droplet is made from water in case of pendant oil droplet and opposite if pendant droplet is made from water.

Table 2: Characteristics of droplets that are used for the creation of CBs

CB No	Upper droplet		Lower droplet		Total volume	Behavior
	Vol. mm ³	Material	Vol. mm ³	Material		
1	0,014	water	0,017	Cedar	0.031	-0.003
2	0,015	water	0,047	Paraffin	0.062	-0.032
3	0,016	cedar	0,044	water	0.06	0.028
4	0,019	paraffin	0,033	water	0.052	0.014
5	0,051	water	0,022	cedar	0.073	0.029
6	0,037	cedar	0,012	water	0.049	-0.025
7	0,036	paraffin	0,013	water	0.049	-0.023
8	0,049	water	0,032	paraffin	0.081	0.017

Figs. 3&4 shows the dynamics of the stretching in macroscopic coordinates $H^* = \frac{H}{r_m}$ as a function of the coordinate $\frac{1}{X}$, according to the derived in previous paper, [17], Eq. (2).

In Fig. 3 is presented investigation of the case of paraffine/oil binary liquid bridges. The two boundary cases are marked with circles (water single bridge) and triangles (paraffine single bridges). The stretching in these two cases takes place with three different speeds: the fastest stretching is marked in green, the slowest: in blue and the intermediate cases are denoted in purple. The two guiding lines, help to follow the trends: "green solid" for water cases and "blue solid" for paraffin cases. We found out that in the case of dynamic stretching (without intermediate stopping for equilibration), the definition domain is not exceeded. However, the points of spontaneous breakage are different for water and paraffin cases. Moreover, we found that at different stretching speeds the breakage takes place at the same points. The binary bridges, made from pendant paraffin droplets (yellow and red triangles) show insignificant dependence on the relative size difference of two initial droplets. The breakage takes place somewhere between breaking points of water and paraffin single bridges, which is clear indication of the overall surface tension modification, possibly because of the oil spreading on the entire CB surface, due to gravity. The opposite cases of pendant water droplets exhibit different behavior: stronger dependence on the initial droplets volume difference as well reduced modification of the surface tension by the oils. The breakage of CB takes place near to the boundary of the definition domain.

Fig. 3 Stretching of binary paraffin/water bridges, compared with stretching of single liquid water and paraffin CBs: for water green, purple and blue circles correspondingly indicate 65.3, 46.4, 38.9 $\mu\text{m/s}$ stretching speed (guided by green solid line); for paraffin green, purple and blue triangles correspondingly indicate 91.9, 70.0, 63.2 $\mu\text{m/s}$ stretching speed (guided by blue solid line); binary CBs No. 4 and 7 in Tab. 2, stretching with 89.8 and 104.6 $\mu\text{m/s}$ marked correspondingly with yellow red triangles (guided with yellow and red dashed curves); binary CBs No. 2 and 8 in Tab. 2, stretching with 59.8 and 99.9 $\mu\text{m/s}$ marked correspondingly with brown and purple rhombs (guided with brown and purple dashed curves).

The case represented in Fig. 4 shows two boundary cases, similarly to Fig. 3, marked with circles (water single bridge, the same cases in Fig. 3) and squares (cedar oil single bridges). The stretching in these two cases takes place again with three different speeds: the fastest cases of stretching are marked with green, the slowest: with blue and the intermediate cases are denoted with purple. The two guiding lines, help to follow the trends: green solid for water cases and the blue solid for cedar oil cases. The breakage of cedar oil CB takes place even closer to the boundary of the definition domain than the water, despite its lower surface tension. This indicates that cedar oil single liquid CBs, is in less extend affected by the speed of increase of the height (in both cases very similar, see description below Fig. 4), compared to single liquid water bridge.

From Fig. 4 is seen that the cases (red and yellow triangles) where the initial pendant droplet is made from water, show reproducible behavior and the structure is so strong that the initiation of the breakage takes place beyond the point of single water bridge breakage.

The other cases of CBs made from cedar oil, pendant droplets show strong dependence on the difference in volume of two initial droplets. This conclusion is based on the fact that the estimated stretching speed in these two cases is almost identical but the behavior of two binary bridges is very different. The brown sequence (No. 3, Tab. 2) with bigger water volume than cedar oil shows behavior that tends to imitate the behavior of water single capillary bridge. The other case of initial upper water pendant droplet but smaller volume than the volume of cedar oil tends to behave as a single volume cedar oil bridge (sequence No. 6, Tab. 3).

Based on the observations of data in Fig. 4, one can conclude that no spreading of the cedar oil on the water surface takes place. In this case, the binary structure of the one, described in Fig. 2b is created, while in the case of paraffin/water binary bridge the water surface is modified additionally by the paraffin surface spreading which leads to the behavior of a new structure with different surface properties than the expectations.

Fig. 4 Stretching of binary cedar oil/water bridges, compared with stretching of single liquid water and cedar oil CBs: for water green, purple and blue circles correspondingly indicate 65.3, 46.4, 38.9 $\mu\text{m/s}$ stretching speed (guided by green solid line); for cedar oil green, purple and blue triangles correspondingly indicate 67.3, 63.6, 50.1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ stretching speed (guided by blue solid line); binary CBs No. 1 and 5 in Tab. 2, stretching with 51.2 and 94.1 $\mu\text{m/s}$ marked correspondingly with yellow red triangles (guided with yellow and red dashed curves); binary CBs No. 3 and 6 in Tab. 2, stretching with 57.3 and 54.5 $\mu\text{m/s}$, marked correspondingly with brown and purple rhombs, (guided with brown and purple dashed curves).

Figure 5 presents samples of CBs stretching. The CBs in Fig. 5a&b show increase of binary cedar oil/water CBs heights. If compare these sequences with single liquids CBs stretching, water (Fig. 5e) and cedar oil (Fig. 5f) the binary bridges behavior resembles more the CBs made from pure oils. This is confirmed with the data, presented in Fig. 4.

From Figs. 5c&d is seen that during CBs stretching, the synergetic effect of two oils mixing appears more significantly if compared with the stretching of the CBs made by single liquids, water (Fig. 5e) and paraffin (Fig. 5f). This indicates that indeed the structures of CBs were modified, which is a way to engineer their surface properties.

Fig. 5 Selected pictures from different CBs stretching: a) sequence No. 3 in Tab. 2; b) sequence No. 5, in Tab. 2; c) sequence No. 8 in Tab. 2; d) sequence No. 2 in Tab. 2; e) sequence of water single capillary bridge; f) sequence of cedar oil CB; g) sequence of paraffin.

6. Summary and conclusions

Binary CBs are interesting engineering structures that can find future application in the industry. The current investigation indicates that creation of the binary CBs is a complicated process that can lead to water surface tension modification by the non-polar liquid and the behavior of the structure is different than the CBs made by source liquids.

We investigated two binary bridges: water/paraffin and water/cedar oil. Our results indicated that water/cedar oil CB is promising structure in terms of Fig. 2b. The results show that despite we assume the negligible influence of the gravity. It strongly affects the behavior of CBs. Our binary structures can overcome the gravity influence, Fig. 5e.

Our further work will be dedicated to development of a suitable theoretical model for prediction of the binary CBs behavior as well as an experimental determination of their surface tension.

6. References

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